

The importance of pipeline transport in the development of social relations

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ANNOTATION

In the article, it is analyzed that the development of pipeline transport is one of the important factors for improving social relations along with work that ensures the sustainable functioning of the economy of our country, and the reason for this is that pipeline transport costs very little, and labor productivity is much higher, and accordingly, the income is at a high level. done

Key words: pipeline, transport, gas, oil, water, population, productivity, economy.

INTRODUCTION

Pipe transport is one of the types of transport used in the modern road communication system. According to information, "The first oil pipeline of local importance was built in the USA in 1865, its length was 6 km." As can be seen from this source, pipeline transport is a relatively new form of transport, as are

other modern forms of transport, such as road, rail and air transport¹. It can be said that the 19th century was a period of great discoveries for mankind. In particular, in the field of transport. In this century, steam locomotives in railways, steam engines in shipbuilding, automobiles and flying devices were created. Among these, we can add pipeline transport.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Well, it's been a little over 150 years since mankind discovered and used pipe transport. According to convincing evidence from many sources, pipelines were originally used to transport oil². Since the first days of the discovery of pipe transport, people have known about its benefits. It is known that other types of transport require constant spending. This is not the case with pipeline transport. People are interested in the fact that the pipeline can be used for many years after it is laid. Because of this feature, over the years, first oil, then natural gas, was transported through pipeline transport. Not only developed, powerful countries, but also developing countries are trying to build pipeline transport and expand it if there is one. Due to its all-round convenience, the use of pipelines in the countries of the world is increasing year by year³. Pipeline transport, which was only 6 km long at the beginning, has grown exponentially. It has become common for countries to own and operate thousands of kilometers of pipelines. On a global

¹ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Фазилбек Қалбай Угли Асанов, & Самандар Куатбай Угли Казаков (2022). ҚУВУР ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ЯХШИЛАШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАРДАН БИРИ СИФАТИДА. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 292-297.

² Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

³ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Фазилбек Қалбай Угли Асанов, & Самандар Куатбай Угли Казаков (2022). ҚУВУР ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ЯХШИЛАШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАРДАН БИРИ СИФАТИДА. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 292-297.

scale, "the total length of gas and oil pipelines is about 2 million kilometers, the main part of which falls on the territory of oil and gas producing countries."

Pipeline transport has a number of advantages over other types of transport⁴:

- the first advantage is the low cost of pipeline transportation, does not require excessive expenses, once laid pipes serve for many years;
- the second advantage is the availability of the shortest routes due to the fact that pipeline transport does not depend on terrain;
- the third advantage, pipeline transport is ecologically safe and does not harm the environment;
- the fourth advantage is the possibility of continuous pipeline transport even over long distances;
- the fifth advantage is that pipeline transport is carried out across the borders of countries without excessive hassle and without various checks;
- the sixth advantage is the ability to transfer liquid and gaseous cargo of any size and quantity in pipeline transport.

At the same time, pipeline transport has its own unique weakness. This is the impossibility of transporting any goods in pipeline transport. Pipeline transport is designed to transport only gaseous and liquid cargoes. However, despite this disadvantage, many countries of the world prefer to use pipeline transport. Countries with these mineral resources are exporting their oil and gas products to foreign countries through direct pipeline transport. For example, the Russian state sends its gas to European countries through main gas pipelines stretching for thousands of kilometers. The length of oil pipelines is relatively less than that of

⁴ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022). САНОАТ, ФАН-ТЕХНИКА ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ТАБИАТ, ЖАМИЯТ ВА ИНСОНИЯТ ҲАЁТИ БИЛАН ДИАЛЕКТИК АЛОҚАДОРЛИГИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 351-358.

gas pipelines⁵. But even then it can stretch for thousands of kilometers. In this case, extracted oil products are transported by pipeline to oil refineries, railway stations and seaports. From there, the oil is transported to the destination in rail tankers and sea tankers. It should also be mentioned that pipeline transport is also used in the internal communication systems of countries. Here is an interesting situation. Have you heard of milk being transported in pipes? It is natural that the answer to this question is no. Because we have seen and known that mainly oil, gas and water are transported by pipeline. However, in some countries, non-traditional cargo - milk is also transported through pipelines. In particular, in the countries of Austria and Sweden, milk is transported downstream from mountain pastures through pipelines. There was a specific economic interest in this approach. First of all, it is necessary to build roads for the movement of tank cars to the high, sloping mountain pastures. Secondly, tanker trucks must be constantly moving on this complex route to transport milk. All of these require money. Also, there is no guarantee that trucks driving on difficult roads will not have an accident. Taking this into account, it was chosen to transport milk in pipelines. It is very economical and, the level of security is also ensured when delivering the cargo to the destination. We also know that most countries use pipeline transport to supply natural gas and drinking water to their residents, enterprises and organizations. Personally, most of us enjoy this convenience of tube transportation. At the same time, natural gas and drinking water are supplied to our houses through pipes⁶. This tool has already proven its effectiveness due to its low cost and convenience. Therefore, all countries of the world are trying to use convenient and cheap

⁵ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Фазилбек Қалбай Угли Асанов, & Самандар Куатбай Угли Казаков (2022). ҚУВУР ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ЯХШИЛАШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАРДАН БИРИ СИФАТИДА. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 292-297.

⁶ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов (2022) ЎЗБЕКИСТОН ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ВА ТРАНСПОРТ ТИЗИМИНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (TSTU Conference 1), 403-407.

pipeline transport as much as possible.

It should be noted that pipeline transport is also important for Uzbekistan⁷. The appearance of pipeline transport in Uzbekistan dates back to 1908. In the same year, the first oil pipeline in the history of our country was laid with a length of 20 kilometers, from the Chimyon oil field to the Altariq oil refinery. This was the prelude to pipeline transport in our country. Over the years, the distance of pipeline transport has also increased. Only, the length of the pipelines from the Altariq oil refinery to other oil fields is 230 kilometers. Later, oil pipelines were laid in other regions of Uzbekistan. For example, there is the Lalmikor - Kumkurgan oil pipeline in Surkhandarya region, the West Rock - North Ortabulak oil pipeline in Kashkadarya region, and the Kokdumalok - Bukhara oil pipeline in Bukhara region.

Construction and operation of gas pipelines in our republic started later than oil pipelines. It corresponds to the early sixties (1960s) of the last century. Although the use of gas pipelines began half a century after oil pipelines, it has grown considerably in scope and volume over the intervening period. The reason for this is the presence of a large number of gas fields rich in reserves in our country. These gas fields, one after the other, were developed step by step. Initially, the laying of gas pipelines was carried out in the directions of local importance. Gas pipelines on the Asaka-Andijan, Khojaabad-Fergana, Northern Sokh-Kokan and Gazli-Kogon routes were among them. Later, the Jargoq-Bukhara-Samarkand-Tashkent and Mubarak-Tashkent gas pipelines covering much longer distances were laid. The laying of gas pipelines in these directions has played a significant role in providing natural gas to economic entities and residents

⁷ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Фазилбек Қалбай Угли Асанов, & Самандар Куатбай Угли Казаков (2022). ҚУВУР ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ЯХШИЛАШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАРДАН БИРИ СИФАТИДА. Academic research in educational sciences, 3 (11), 292-297.

of the Republic⁸. The abundance of natural gas in the existing gas fields in our country made it possible to export natural gas to foreign countries. Main gas pipelines have been laid to send gas to a number of countries⁹. In particular, "Gas pipelines transferred from Uzbekistan to the Urals (2100 km) and Moscow (3500 km) occupy one of the first places in the world in terms of diameter and length". In addition, our country is connected with the neighboring countries of Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan and China through pipeline transport. Among these countries, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan and Afghanistan are supplied with our natural gas. The transit of pipeline transport of Uzbekistan is being used effectively. This is reflected in the supply of natural gas through the pipeline from Turkmenistan to China through Uzbekistan. All this is evidence that pipeline transport in our country has grown from a local level to an international level.

CONCLUSION

The presence of interstate main gas pipelines and the fact that we export natural gas through them have positive aspects for the following social relations¹⁰:

- firstly, it ensures the stability of our relations with countries supplying natural gas;

⁸ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. - P.406-410.

⁹ Бахриддин Лутфуллаевич Салимов, Фазилбек Қалбай Угли Асанов, & Самандар Куатбай Угли Казаков (2022). ҚУВУР ТРАНСПОРТИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИ ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРНИ ЯХШИЛАШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАРДАН БИРИ СИФАТИДА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3 (11), 292-297.

¹⁰ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. *Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси*. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

- secondly, it is the basis for increasing the prestige of our country at the international level;
- thirdly, it serves to increase the export potential of our country;
- fourthly, it is an important source of foreign exchange funds necessary for the economy of our country;
- fifthly, the existence and operation of these main gas pipelines allowed to provide employment to hundreds and maybe thousands of our citizens.

So, the development of pipeline transport is one of the important factors for the improvement of social relations along with work that ensures the sustainable functioning of the economy of our country. This is because pipeline transport costs are very low, and labor productivity is very high. Accordingly, the income is guaranteed to be high.

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